

Assessing Testing Skills Among Senior Secondary School Teachers in Cross River Central Senatorial District, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated testing skills among senior secondary schools Teachers in Cross River Central Senatorial District. Specifically the study determined whether senior secondary schools teachers adhere to relevant testing skills in test construction. Descriptive survey research design was adopted while the population of the study comprised (1,887 teachers in all the 119 public secondary schools in the state). A sample size of 188 teachers was selected using proportionate stratified random sampling method. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researchers. The (content validity) of the research instrument was ascertained by expert judgement while reliability was established using the Cronbach's alpha statistical technique and a coefficient of 0.73 was obtained. The researchers personally administered the instrument to the teachers in the selected schools. Data was analyzed using mean, and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed that, senior secondary school teachers in Cross River State possess and use to a large extent the testing skills needed in test construction when constructing their classroom achievement tests. It was recommended that frequent workshops and seminar on testing skills should be organized for teachers on a regular basis.

Keywords: Testing Skill, Achievement Test, Senior Secondary, Teacher, Test Construction

Introduction

The effectiveness of a teacher made -test in providing information needed regarding students' performance, is closely linked with the procedures followed in the test construction. This underscores why teachers are exposed to the basic principles of test construction during the teacher education programme, and even after graduation in workshops and seminars. The course "Educational Tests and Measurement" is a requirement for graduation from teachers' education programme in institutions. The basic reason behind such exposure is to equip the teachers with the necessary testing skills in test construction and competencies such as to define the purpose of the test, prepared the test blue print, determine the item format to use, determine what is to be tested, write the individual items, review the items, prepare the scoring key, write directions, and evaluate the test so that in the course of teaching, they can obtain and report valid, reliable and useful information concerning learners' achievement. In the management of schools in Nigeria, teachers, schools' management and policymakers in the course of or after teaching and sometimes before classroom teaching need to make decisions concerning teaching and learning. These decisions are made based on information gathered from the students' learning. Generally, this information gathering procedure denotes assessment. Assessment is defined as a process of gathering data to better understand the strengths and weaknesses of student learning. Assessment is a means whereby the teacher obtains information about knowledge gains, behavioral changes and other aspects of the development of learners (Oguneye, 2022). In education, the term assessment refers to the wide variety of methods or tools that educators use to evaluate, measure, and document the academic readiness, progress, skill, acquisition, or educational needs of students (Filkins, 2013). In assessing leaning outcomes testing may become a necessary tool.

Testing has always been an essential part of education. The concept of testing can be viewed as a set of tasks presented to a person, the performance of which depends on the possessions of a particular body of knowledge and skills. Testing in education is not an end in itself, but a means to an end (Uyigue,2021).

Test is a tool to measure the knowledge level of students and adjust the learning material accordingly, such test contains series of questions. The questions can differ in form or format, but at the end, students are expected to answer the questions in order to graded and see how much they have learnt. According to Anikweze (2010) Test is any kind of device for measuring ability, achievement, interest and other traits. The purpose of a test is to be able to give valid information on the students' abilities and knowledge. Hence, the success of teaching and learning can be seen in the test's results. Testing

therefore, provides useful information for decision making about students, teachers and the programme.

The need for tests can be categorised into educational and non-educational needs. Amedahe and Gyimah (2016) and Nitko (2018) have classified educational uses of tests into instructional management decisions, classification decisions, placement decisions, Counselling guidance decisions, and credentialing and certification decisions. The instructional management decisions refer to all the class room decisions taken by the teacher on the basis of the assessment results of students. Firstly, tests provide useful information for instructional diagnosis and remediation. According to Nitko, (2018) diagnosis involves identifying both the appropriate content and the features of the learning activities in which a student should be engaged to attain the learning target. Secondly, tests are used in the modelling of learning targets. The teacher can then teach his students to detect the ways in which their performance is matching the desired performance and the ways in which it is deficient. As a diagnostic tool test indicate how prepared students are to profit from new instruction and to what degree they've mastered previous concepts and skills. Thirdly, tests are needed for the provision of motivation for students, rewarding those who have prepared well in advance and providing negative consequences for those who have not prepared well. The frequency of an individual's behaviour is increased by reinforcement. Hence, it can be reasonably concluded that tests cause students to study more in the sense that the motivation derived from tests as a result of performing well can activate and direct their learning by sustaining their interest. Fourthly, tests are used for the assignment of grades to students. The grades or symbols (A, B, C,) that the classroom teacher reports, represent his /her formal evaluation or judgement of the quality or worth of his/her students 'achievement of the important learning objectives (Amedahe & Gyimah, 2016; Nitko, 2018). On the issue of selection decisions, sometimes, an institution decides whether or not some persons are acceptable for specific programmes. Test in education can be classified into two broad types achievement and psychological. Achievement test are tests that are administered with reference to a specified content or body of knowledge. There are two types of achievement tests: Teacher made test and standardized test. Teacher made achievement tests are test designed by the instructor, it is criterion referenced in that he sets a point of success or failure without regard to the performance of others within the group or outside the group being tested. While standardized achievement tests are design by experts for a large population where performance of testees are

determined by how other test takers perform in the test, it is norm referenced. Standardized test or teacher made test can either be essay test type or objective type. The essay test type is where students are given the opportunity to organize their taught and present same in a logical and persuasive manner with little or no restrictions. While the objectives test limits the student to a specific pattern or response or even provide alternatives from which testees pick the alternatives he considers the correct answer. (Omorogiuwa, 2019).

Psychological tests are tests designed to measure inherent traits in an individual without reference to a defined content or body of knowledge. But items in the test should be measuring the trait in question. They are used to assess traits, certain condition(s) of the individual, intelligence (how quickly and accurately an individual can respond to items), aptitude, achievements, attitudes (predisposition to act in a particular manner. For example, demonstration of trait of love, hate, anger, and honesty), feelings, interests (values and preferences of individual), and special abilities such as skills (Osarumwense, 2022).

Achievement test are designed to determine the extent to which the content of a course an individual has learned over a period of time (Adeniji & Llorah, 2018). Achievement tests are the tests that are designed to measure the knowledge gained based on a defined content usually after an instrumental process. In the school setting, a test is generally used as an assessment tool for obtaining information about students' learning. It should be made clear at this point that testing is a key component in educational assessment. These tests are normally administered to students after a period of instruction. The significance of test construction is close to that of evaluating students' performance because it reflects the effectiveness and professionalism of an educator (Atta, 2023). There are numerous testing skills that need to be applied in constructing tests. These include, defining the purpose of the test, determine the item format to use, writing the test blue print, determine what is to be tested, write the individual items, review the items, prepare the scoring key, write directions, and evaluate the test An ideal construction of any test must begin by defining the variables or constructs to be measured and specifying the test content (Ali, 2017).

According to Gronlund (1988) cited in Okyireh (2008), the key to effective achievement testing is careful planning. It is during the planning stage that the purpose of the test must be determined.

Instructional objectives need to be defined in terms of student behaviours and linked to what has been stressed in class. It is worthy of note, however, that each type of test use typically requires some modification of the test design and thereby determines the type of item format to be used. The second step of the skills in test construction is the determination of the item format to use. The most common item formats in classroom achievement testing are the essay- and the objective-types. According to Etsey (2014), it is sometimes necessary to use more than one item format in a single test. This is because depending on the purpose of the test, one item format cannot be used exclusively to measure all learning outcomes. According to Etsey (2014), the teacher at this point should determine the chapters or units of the course content that the test should cover as well as the knowledge, skills or attitudes to be measured. Instructional objectives need to be defined in terms of student behaviors and linked to what has been stressed in class. A test plan made up of a table of specifications should be made. The table of specifications matches the course content with the instructional objectives (Etsey, 2014). With the total number of items on the test in mind, the specification table helps to avoid overlapping in the construction of the test items, helps to determine the weighting of learning outcomes with respect to content areas, and makes sure that justice is done to all aspects of the course, thereby helping to ensure the content validity of the test. Next, is the actual writing of the individual test items. Tamakloe et al, (1996) cited in Okyire,(2008) and Etsey, (2014) have pointed out that whichever test item types that are being constructed must follow the basic principles laid down for them. There are, however, general guidelines that according to Mehrens and Lehmann (2015) and Etsey (2014), apply to all types of tests. These include:

The table of specifications must be kept before the teacher and continually referred to as the items are written. The test items must be related to and match the instructional objectives. Well-defined items that are not vague and ambiguous must be formulated. Grammar and spelling errors must be checked. Textbook or stereotyped language must be avoided. Excessive verbiage and complex sentences must be avoided. The test items must be based on information that students should know. More items that are actually needed in the test must be prepared in the initial draft. The test items must be written in advance (at least two weeks) of the testing date to permit reviews and editing Basseyy and Idaka, (2017) has suggested that the items must be critically examined at least a week after writing them. He has emphasized that where possible, fellow teachers or colleagues in the same subject area should review

the test items. Reviewing and editing the items are for the purpose of removing or rewording poorly constructed items, checking difficulty level of items, checking the length of the test, and the discrimination level of the items (items must discriminate between low and high-achievers). All test items should be checked for technical errors and irrelevant clues. After reviews and editing, the test items can now be assembled. In assembled the test, the items must be arranged in order of increasing difficulty. The scoring keys must be written as early as possible after assembling the test.

Immediately following the preparation of the scoring keys, is the writing of clear and concise directions for the entire test and sections of the test. Here, the time limit for the test must be clearly stated. The last stage of the test construction process is the evaluation of the test on the criteria of clarity, validity, practicality, efficiency and fairness. Clarity refers to how simply and clearly the items are written vis-à-vis the ability level of the testees and the material the test is measuring. It also refers to the kinds of knowledge the test is measuring and how adequately the test items relate to the content and course objectives (Amedahe & Gyimah, 2016). Validity bothers on how closely the test represents the material presented in the course unit or chapter and how faithfully the test reflects the difficulty level of the material taught in class. The issue of validity here establishes the content validity evidence of the test. On practicality, consideration is given to whether students will have enough time to complete the test. It also bothers on whether there are enough materials (chairs, tables, and answer booklets) to present the test and complete it effectively (Amedahe & Gyimah, 2016). Efficiency bothers on finding out whether the test is the best way to measure the desired knowledge, skill or attitude. Consideration must also be given to the problems that might arise due to material difficulty or shortage and these expected problems well catered for (Amedahe & Gyimah, 2016; Tamakloe et al., 1996 cited in Okyire 2009). On fairness criterion, consideration is given to whether students have been given advance notice of the test, whether students have been adequately prepared for the test, and whether students understand the testing procedures. Consideration is also given to how the lives of students are affected as a result of the possible uses to which the test scores are put (Amedahe & Gyimah, 2016). After this comprehensive evaluation of the test, the test can be submitted to be processed for subsequent administration.

Considering the sensitive role that information from a test play in making educational decisions for students as well as management, it is important to say that both test developers and users must make conscious effort to improve the validity and the reliability of the test using testing skills in order to get

objective information that approximate the individual's true characteristic, which the test developer seeks to estimate. Testing skills are, therefore, intrinsic tools in the educational venture. These skills apply to all types of tests – diagnostic, formative and summative. It is therefore necessary that all teachers should follow as well as apply these skills in their interactions with learners if success is the target in the teaching and learning enterprise, and if the results of their test must be objective in revealing teaching-learning effectiveness. These testing skills in test construction are however steps in preparing valid, reliable and useful test items. Test construction implies a systematic process of assembling test items or the preparation for a test by drawing and compiling series of questions which constitute the task for the testees. An ideal construction of any test must begin by defining the variables or constructs to be measured and specifying the test content (Ali, 2017). Test construction need careful consideration of specific purposes of test, since test serves many different purposes. In this study, it is most needful that test designers particularly teachers adhere to define the purpose of the test, prepared the test blue print, determine the item format to use, determine what is to be tested, write the individual items, review the items, prepare the scoring key, write directions, and evaluate the test.

Hamman-Tukurl and Hamafyelta (2015) assessed teacher's competence in test construction and content validity of teachers made examination questions in commerce in Borno state; The finding reveals that the teachers in Borno state senior secondary school were not competent in constructing their examination questions based on the limited National Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) standards. The teacher's examination question had low content validity that emphasized lower levels of cognitive domain remembering, understanding and applying.

Afemikhe and Imobekhai (2018) examine teachers' utilization of test construction procedures for validity improvement of achievement test. The study showed that teachers ignore some aspects of achievement test construction procedures. They however apply some procedures recommended for test construction. Variations on some few aspects of the procedures were however noticed between primary and secondary school teachers and between beginning and experienced teachers. In the same vein, Tariah and Okon (2019) carried out a study to investigate knowledge of test construction procedure among lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt; They found out that the lecturers are very knowledgeable on the test construction procedures but observation of most tests constructed by lecturers in the university showed that their tests lack basic psychometric properties. It

was concluded that, they probably do not apply the knowledge during the test construction for their respective courses.

Frank, Isaac, and Francis (2019) carry out an investigation on teachers' test construction practices of Senior High Schools (SHS) teachers in the Cape Coast Metropolis. Using a qualitative document analysis, samples of End-of-Term Examination papers in Integrated Science, Core Mathematics and Social Studies in three selected SHS in the Cape Coast Metropolis. The results revealed that the teachers have limited knowledge in the construction of end-of-term examination. This was evident as issues were found with the content representativeness and relevance of the test, reliability, and fairness of the assessment tasks which were evaluated.

Fehintola, (2022) assessed senior secondary school test construction procedures and testing practice in Oyo State. The results showed that, to a great extent, teachers were not aware of the test construction principles. In a similar study, Uyigue, (2022) investigated the test construction and administration competencies of teachers and found that the teachers are high in them and that; there were no significant differences in these competencies when compared based on the Professional Qualification and Years of Teaching Experiences of the teachers.

Research Question

1. What are the relevant testing skills adhered to by senior secondary school teachers when constructing classroom achievement tests?

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of the study comprised of all public secondary schools teachers (1,887) in Cross River Central Senatorial District (Cross River State Zonal Ministry of Education Ikom, 2024). A sample size of 188 teachers was selected using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was “Assessing of Testing Skills Questionnaire” (ATSQ). The research instrument was a self-design questionnaire containing 8 items on test construction. The items on the questionnaire were on a four point Liker type scale. The items on the four point Liker scale were scored ranging from “Always to Never” for which the respondents indicate their position with 4= Always, 3 = Very often, 2= Sometime, and 1 = Never.. To ensure the content validity, copies of the instrument were given to

three experts in measurement and evaluation. They were asked to look at the adequacy of the items in line with the purpose, and research questions. The internal consistency was then estimated using Cronbach's alpha statistics and a reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained. The researchers personally visited the 24 selected public secondary schools and a total of 188 questionnaires were administered to the teachers in their respective staff rooms and the questionnaires were collected immediately by the researcher. The research question was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. 160 copies of the questionnaire adequately filled by the respondents were used for the analysis.

Results

The data collected is analyzed and the result is presented and discussed here under.

Research Question

1. What are the relevant testing skills adhered to by senior secondary school teachers when constructing classroom achievement tests?

Table 1: Descriptive in Mean and Standard Deviation of the Testing Skills in test construction adhered to by Senior Secondary School Teachers

		Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Ranking	Remarks
1	I ensure that all important content areas are covered as well as instructional objective of the test	3.20	1.09	1 st	√
2	I determine what type of item format to be used	3.20	.91	2 nd	√
3	I determine alongside the weight that should be assigned to each item	3.07	.98	3 rd	√
4	I provide clear instructions to the students on how the test is to be responded to.	2.72	1.01	4 th	√
5	I write out the test items first as draft	2.35	1.15	5 th	X
6	I write out the final test items	2.34	1.06	6 th	X
7	I review and edit the items	1.97	1.13	7 th	X
8	I evaluate the test	1.86	1.10	8 th	X

N = 160; Item cut-off Mean = 2.50 √ = Adhered, x = Not adhered

Table 1 showed the descriptive data of relevant testing skills adhered to by senior secondary school teachers when constructing classroom achievement tests. From the table, items one to four have means greater than the cut-off item mean of 2.5; this implies that the respondents answered in affirmation, the means ranged from 2.72 to 3.20 with SD as 1.01- 1.09. While items five to eight have means less than the cut-off item mean of 2.5; this implies that the respondents answered in the negative, the means ranged from 1.86 to 2.35 with SD as 1.10-1.15. from these analyses , the teachers ensures content coverage, determine items format, weights and provide clear instructions, however, they don't prepare draft before writing the final items neither do they edit or review the items or evaluate before administration. Hence, this shows that senior secondary school teachers in Cross River State adhered to a considerable number of the relevant testing skills in test construction and ignore other aspects of the skills.

Discussion of Findings

The findings show that senior secondary school teachers in Cross River State adhered to a considerable number of the relevant testing skills in test construction and ignore other aspects of the skills. This could be on account of the teachers not having knowledge of all the skills in test construction. This could be depicted to mean as the teachers not giving adequate training and regular workshops on testing skills in test construction. The finding of this study is in agreement with the findings of Afemikhe and Imobekhai (2018) that showed that teachers ignore some aspects of achievement construction procedures. They however apply some procedures recommended for test construction. The finding is also in agreement with the findings of Tariah and Okon (2019) they found out that the lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt are very knowledgeable on the test construction procedures but observation of most tests constructed by lecturers in the university showed that their tests lack basic psychometric properties. Again the finding of this study corroborated with the findings of Frank, Isaac, and Francis (2019) which revealed that teachers have limited knowledge in the construction of end-of-term examination. This was evident as issues were found with the content representativeness and relevance of the test, reliability, and fairness of the assessment tasks which were evaluated.

However, the result from research question one is in disagreement with the study of Fehintola (2022). The results of the study showed that, to a great extent, teachers were not aware of the test construction principles. Also, the results showed that, the teachers were not aware of the meaning of test construction terminologies. The finding also disagree with the finding of Hamman-Tukurl and Hamafyelta (2015), which reveals that, the teachers in Borno State senior secondary school were not competent in constructing their examination questions based on the limited National Educational Scientific and Cultural organization (UNESCO) standards. The teacher's examination question had low content validity that emphasized lower levels of cognitive domain remembering, understanding and applying. But on the contrary the finding differs from Uyigue (2022) who found that teachers in Edo South Senatorial District are competent in test development skills.

The findings from this study may not be farfetched as the teachers put to use the basic principles that are relatively easy to apply neglecting those that are more demanding in application in terms of empirical application. It is presumed that the knowledge of test construction is well known to the teachers, however, the practical application of these skills is the problem for obvious reasons, which may range from attitude, low level of teachers motivation among others.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that senior secondary school teachers adhered to a considerable number of the testing skills in test construction and ignored other aspects of the skills. (The teacher adhered to all important content areas as well as instructional objective of the test, determine what type of item format to be used, determine alongside the weight that should be assigned to each item, provide clear instructions to the students on how the test is to be responded to, and did not adhered to writing out the test items first as draft, writing out the final test items, review and edit the items, and evaluate the test).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Frequent workshops and seminar on testing skills in test construction should be organized for teachers regularly. To re-echoes the need for the application of these skill in test construction.
2. Principals in the secondary school should ensure that teachers apply these skills in their entirety in test construction.

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